

Methodological Considerations of Digital Ethnographic Studies in the AI Music Field

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Abstract

As music generation systems driven by artificial intelligence (AI) gain popularity, understanding how users engage with these platforms is essential for examining the emerging practices surrounding AI music. This paper reflects on our ongoing digital ethnographic research conducted on the AI music platforms Suno and Boomy and their corresponding Discord discussion forums. We propose an AI music landscape that illustrates the interaction between users, platforms, and music-related activities, and examine two user groups: Boomy users who create tracks, and Suno users who create AI metal music. We critically analyse the challenges we encounter throughout the process regarding accessing and gatekeeping, trust-building, and the blurred positionality of researchers. We reflect on our experiences and propose methods for immersion and adaptation in AI music research. This study contributes to the refinement of digital ethnographic methodologies for the diverse field of AI music and encourages ongoing reflection on research strategies in AI music studies.

1 Introduction

Commercial music generation systems powered by artificial intelligence (AI) have expanded significantly in recent years.¹ Platforms such as Suno, Udio, Boomy, and many more, enable individuals to generate music tailored to their preferences. As a result, the volume of AI-generated music (herein termed *AI music*) has increased substantially (Tencer, 2024). At the same time, digital service providers such as Spotify, Pandora, and YouTube use AI to generate personalized playlists; and platforms like TikTok use AI to create background music for video content. Such features significantly enhance user engagement and interaction on social media (Mokoena and Obagbuwa, 2025). In addition, the growing user base of AI music platforms has given rise to active forums and communities on social platforms such as Discord and Reddit. It is such user activities that shape what constitutes AI music, which makes essential in-depth and critical explorations to understand the motivations and values behind such practices (Sturm et al., 2024).

Digital ethnographic methods have grappled with the complexities of online studies of communities for decades (e.g. Hine 2015; Kozinets 2010; Pink et al. 2016; Hjorth et al. 2016). Still, there seem to be some aspects of AI music communities that differ from other digital music fields. In our work, we are applying digital ethnography to study users of AI music platforms, the online communities in which AI music creation and discussions are taking place, and the interactions between users and these platforms—what we term the *AI music landscape*. In this work, drawing on our experiences and the challenges encountered, we ask two main questions: 1) What is the AI music landscape and what activities and practices are emerging from it? 2) What are some methodological strategies for the ethnographic study of the AI music landscape?

¹Zhao and Kanhov share equal contributions as the first authors of this paper. Sturm contributed to the overall direction of the paper, with a particular writing focus in section 3.2.

In the following sections, we begin by outlining the background of digital ethnographic methodologies. Building on our mapping of the AI music landscape, we then present case studies focused on two distinct user groups: Boomy users creating tracks, and Suno users who specialize in AI metal music. During our digital ethnography, we encountered several challenges, including accessing and gatekeeping, trust-building, and the blurred positionality of researchers. We investigate the reasons why digital communities are challenging to access and to conduct ethnographic research within. We propose practical methodologies for AI music researchers by emphasizing multidimensional immersion and the dynamic adaptation of positionality throughout the digital ethnographic process. Overall, this work contributes to refining digital ethnographic methodologies, specifically tailored to the diverse field of AI music communities, with the goal of encouraging ongoing reflection on research strategies in AI music studies (Sturm et al., 2024).

2 Background

2.1 Digital Ethnographic Methodologies

Digital ethnography applies qualitative methods, such as participant observation and interviews, to study people and their social lives in digital spaces (Hine, 2015; Kozinets, 2010; Pink et al., 2016; Hjorth et al., 2016). As Born and Haworth (2017b) argue, the term has a dual meaning: it not only refers to ethnographic research conducted in digital spaces but also encompasses the development and application of digital methodologies to enhance ethnographic inquiry. In this context, “digital” refers to “forms of networked and mediated socialization” (Forberg and Schilt, 2023, p.2), reflecting how digital ethnographic methods have emerged in response to the profound transformations in social interactions brought about by online and digital life. This change requires adaptations of the study of social and cultural interaction in digital spaces and sensitivity towards the affordances of technology (Bucher and Helmond, 2018).

Navigating privacy and informed consent becomes more challenging as identities are obscured online (Hine, 2015; Kendall, 1999), which is further complicated by the fact that interaction with participants is mediated by the online spaces and, in most cases, textual data (Garcia et al., 2009). The rapid changes in virtual worlds, along with the shifting nature of user experiences and social interactions, further complicates the research process and the distinction between genuine, ironic, or sarcastic content (Boellstorff et al., 2012; Colley and Moore, 2022). Debates about whether online data is private or public, if collected data should be anonymized to protect the privacy of users, and the ethical aspects around “lurking” and observing users without the researchers identifying themselves or their presence, require further consideration (Cera, 2023; Forberg and Schilt, 2023; Eynon et al., 2017). These aspects can also cause practices of gatekeeping (Wallace, 2018; Järvekülg and Wikström, 2022; Tyft, 2021), performed either by the companies or the participants one studies, making it difficult to enter communities or have certain types of interaction.

Positionality has further been recognized as a key component in qualitative research, prompting researchers to critically examine their relationship to “the other” (Collins and McNulty, 2020). In ethnography, this is related to the term “reflexivity”, where the ethnography is viewed as co-produced between researchers and their participants, and where the researcher critically examines their role, assumptions and influence on the research process (Davies, 2007). Positionality unfolds as a continuous process shaped by ongoing negotiation between the researcher and participants during ethnographic inquiry (Lavoragna and Sugiura, 2022). In digital spaces, however, this process becomes increasingly complex due to the blurred boundaries between online and offline experiences, and the fluid identities of researchers being both users of platforms and researchers at the same time. Digital ethnography thus holds a two-fold realization: firstly, the socializing processes in digital spaces are different from those in offline settings, and secondly, these spaces require adaptive methodologies for those socializing processes to be revealed (Quinton and Reynolds, 2017).

2.2 The AI Music Landscape

When conducting digital ethnography on AI music, our key focus is on the users who engage in AI music generation, the types of music they generate, the music-related activities taking place, and how these are afforded by platforms. These elements together form an evolving landscape—what

we term the *AI music landscape*.² With the rise of digital media in recent decades, the idea of a digital landscape has evolved to capture the complex and interconnected flows of information, exchanges, and meanings across both offline and online spaces, reflecting the cultural, political, and epistemic processes that shape them (Webster et al., 2020). Building on Cavazza’s annual *Social Media Landscape* (2024) and Sackl-Sharif’s *Digital Metal Landscape* (2021), we propose an AI music landscape to map the richness and dynamics of AI music practice. This framework offers an overview of the platforms shaping AI music practice and the digital activities of AI music users with whom we engage, and can help provide a more comprehensive and interconnected view based on our observations.

The AI music landscape encompasses a range of digital tools, platforms, and applications supporting AI music practices. It comprises five sections: music making, music sharing, livestreaming, social media, and online forums. The core music-making section includes Boomy and Suno as well as a growing number of platforms actively shaping the market. Social and coding platforms such as Discord, Reddit, and GitHub are integral to this landscape, enabling users to share AI music creations, exchange techniques and information, build communities, and organize and participate in online activities. The official Discord servers for Suno and Boomy are moderated by the companies, while forums on Reddit and GitHub are more often user-created. Music and video sharing platforms, including YouTube (Music), Spotify, SoundCloud, Bandcamp, and Tidal, offer additional spaces where users can upload and distribute their music to reach audiences and potentially earn revenue for their creations. Some users also livestream their AI music creation process on Twitch, interacting with others in real-time, or reviewing their favorite AI music from their communities. Finally, social media platforms and link aggregation tools like X (formerly Twitter), Facebook, Instagram, and Linktree are often linked to users’ profiles on AI music generation platforms, enabling the sharing of music, photos, and personal networks. Rather than remaining confined to a single space, most AI music users maintain a presence across multiple platforms. For example, their Discord profiles often link to accounts on various other sites, illustrating their involvement in diverse practices. User engagement is thus shaped by online social networks and the specific affordances of each platform, enabling them to navigate a range of interconnected spaces. Taken together, this AI music landscape illustrates the complexity and diversity of user practices, underscoring the dynamic interplay between users, platforms, and music-making processes.

3 Case Studies

3.1 Our Methodological Approaches

In our digital ethnography, we focus on platforms for AI music generation, specifically Boomy and Suno, and the social digital forum Discord, where some of this music is shared and discussed. These platforms serve as field sites, functioning as the “stage on which the social processes under study take place” (Burrell, 2009, p.182). They are also the fields where we, as ethnographers, conduct our digital ethnographic research.

While digital ethnography often emphasizes the complex interrelation between online and offline life (Hine, 2015; Miller and Slater, 2000), our experience of AI music practices belongs to a small body of research that focuses on music cultures and practices that exist solely in online spaces (e.g. Born and Haworth 2017a,b; Waldron 2018; Dewan et al. 2017; Beekhuyzen et al. 2011). At least, we have yet to see much offline activity emerge from and intermingle with these online practices. Our studies incorporate several methods of digital ethnography to approach these digital fields, including ethnographic observations, semi-structured interviews via Zoom, written responses via email, and autoethnographic approaches (Ellis, 2004) where we become users of these platforms and participants in the online discussion spaces. Our ethnographic work is supported by an EU-funded project (see Acknowledgments), which required the submission and approval of deliverables about our ethical practices, such as participant recruitment, data collection and management, and profiling. Details of our methods were reviewed by an internal review board at our host institution, which ultimately concluded: “By the criteria stated in the Swedish Ethical Review act (SFS 2003:460), this project does not need an ethics permit, or can get such a permit.”

²The concept of landscape originates from Sauer’s (1963) idea of cultural landscape, which emphasizes the interplay between human culture and the physical environment.

When observing participants and their activity online we have made minimal interaction and thus not disclosed our presence as researchers so as not to affect the discussions (Cera, 2023). Therefore, users—who are also participants in our study—have not given their informed consent to be observed. At the same time, we have only undisclosedly observed platforms where posts and discussions are publicly accessible (Grincheva, 2017). When applying autoethnographic approaches, we try to minimize our interaction with other users and only post non-critical messages that are often positive about our experience working with a platform. When we contact users directly, however, we are clear about our identities as researchers, and each informant reads an information sheet and signs a consent form before any interview.³ In this ongoing work, we have so far interviewed around 10 informants in a semi-structured format. Typical questions we ask are: Who are you, and what is your musical background? Can you describe your AI musical practice? Which AI tools do you use and how? Are you part of any communities related to your practice?

Before moving on to our case studies, we provide information about our backgrounds to give a more detailed picture of who is doing ethnography in this work. Zhao is a musicologist and classically trained pianist, specializing in ethnomusicology and subcultural studies. Kanhov is a musicologist with a background in contemporary art music, philosophy, and feminist theory. Sturm is an engineering researcher working for many years in the domains of computer music, and is also a composer.

3.2 AI Music from Boomy

Boomy⁴ has been operating since being launched in late 2019, and offers a unique opportunity to its users: to make money from streams of music they generate using the system. To make music, users of the Boomy platform select from a variety of options, such as instrumentation, tempo, and “density” of certain elements, e.g., percussion. Users are also able to upload a sound file that can be modified and mixed with a Boomy-generated track. Boomy manages a Discord server providing several forums for users to share and discuss their music, receive feedback, communicate with other users, and participate in events and contests organized by Boomy A&R. Channels include “general” (“A place to chat about anything music and non-music related (No promo!)”), “song-sharing” (“Share your Boomy songs!”), and “music-feedback” (“Provide and receive constructive feedback on boomy songs and content”). For some time, a regular event was “Workshop Wednesdays”, where for an hour users could post their Boomy tracks and receive feedback from A&R. Other events included holiday-themed contests. One was the 2023 “Spooktacular” contest where Halloween-themed entries were judged by A&R, and winners were given prizes, such as t-shirts or subscriptions to the service.

Since September 2023 we have been observing and participating in this space, and using it to find potential informants to interview. Our first attempt to find informants was by posting as ourselves (university researchers) a link to an online survey about AI music. We received only a few responses before Boomy requested we take down the survey because of its focus on Boomy—it could be misinterpreted as coming from or being sponsored by the company. At the same time, we began using an autoethnographic approach to study how Boomy could be used to make music, and how the Discord community operates. We did this as anonymous users for two reasons: 1) the rules posted by Boomy on the use of their Discord server prohibit disclosing personal details; and 2) Boomy would treat us as normal users rather than as researchers seeking to understand their platform and business model.

We began contacting users as ourselves through private messaging on Discord, first sending them a link to our survey, and then asking if they would be interested in being interviewed about how they are using AI in their music. Specific informants that have participated in our semi-structured interviews include a person interested in making music inspired by llamas and alpacas, and their personal experiences in Peru; a person who once played in rock bands but now makes electronic music solo; and a person who came to the Boomy Discord from the Suno Discord because of the negativity they perceived on the latter.

³This procedure, its materials, and the data we are collecting have been reviewed by our institution’s internal review board and assessed as not needing any special ethical considerations because of its low risk to participants.

⁴<https://boomy.com>, last accessed 2025-03-31

3.3 AI Metal Music from Suno

Among AI music generation platforms, Suno is a relatively recent entrant (launched in early 2023), but it has quickly demonstrated strong user appeal and commercial potential (Tencer, 2024). Suno allows users to create music audio from textual prompts. We selected Suno as the primary field for conducting digital ethnography on AI metal music for two key reasons. First, in terms of AI metal music practices, discussions on the official Discord servers of Suno, Boomy, and Udio indicate that Suno hosts the most active and diverse engagement of the three. A search for the keyword “metal” on the Suno official server yields 47,350 relevant results, significantly surpassing Udio’s 7,954 results and Boomy’s 26.⁵ Second, Suno is the only platform that has fostered the emergence of two active, independent AI metal music servers on Discord: “Cyber Metal Radio” and the “Web3 Metal AI & Blockchain Community”. The former is described as “a community-run radio station that’s bringing you the heaviest, most brutal tracks straight from the heart of the suno metal underground!”.⁶ The latter centers on the integration of “blockchain music, AI-generated melodies, and Web3 innovations”.⁷

Metal appears to be among the most popular and actively generated genres on the Suno platform, as evidenced by discussions in Suno’s official Discord server. In the “Genres” forum of its “Showcase” channel, where users engage in discussions based on various music genres, the “Metal” genre dominates with 19,252 posts, significantly outpacing the second most-discussed genre, “Hip-hop/Rap” (4,155 posts).⁸

Beginning in October 2024 one of us initially accessed the official Suno server using an account named after their first name. By observing posts, discussions, and users related to metal music within the server, we quickly identified several active users who shared their AI metal works, organized metal music competitions, and recruited new members for the two AI metal communities. We applied to join the communities, and the moderators permitted us to access their independent Discord servers. In addition to observing metal-related content and practices across the three servers, we also contacted active users through private messaging to recruit informants and conduct interviews.

Based on our observations, these two AI metal communities were established and are managed by a few active, dedicated individuals who serve as moderators. An informant stated that they chose to create their own AI metal music communities outside of the official Suno server because it is too hectic for meaningful community building. Additionally, they felt that Suno moderators have unfairly scrutinized the metal community. Under the moderators’ organization, the communities regularly host activities, particularly various AI metal music contests. Notable examples include “Cyber Metal Radio’s Weekly Top 15 Countdown Show”, “W3M Dubstep Metal Contest”, and “Mosh Call & Breakdown W3M Suno Challenge”. Tracks with the most votes, clicks, and plays are added to the corresponding playlists, shared in the communities, and reviewed by moderators during livestreams. It can be observed that the communities’ moderators and some core members actively participate in these competitions as their works frequently appear in the winning playlists.

In terms of the metal music generated, most Suno metal-focused users exhibit a consistent preference for this style. In other words, metal-related prompts dominate the majority of their generations, such as #heavy metal, #power metal and #distorted guitar. Furthermore, a significant trend of hybrid music experimentation has been observed, as users frequently label their creations as “experimental” when sharing them on the platform. Suno’s metal-focused users use the platform’s integration capabilities to blend metal music with genres and elements that are rarely combined in offline practices. In this way, experimental and unconventional musical practices are facilitated and encouraged by Suno (Tan, 2024). Notable examples include “bluegrass metal”, which incorporates instruments such as the banjo, dobro, mandolin, and fiddle; cyber metal, which blends anime-inspired electronic rock and rap metal; and Chinese metal, which features Mandarin lyrics and the timbre of various traditional Chinese folk instruments.⁹

⁵Last accessed 2025-03-28.

⁶<https://cybermetalradio.com/>, last accessed 2025-04-01.

⁷<https://web3metal.beehiiv.com/>, last accessed 2025-04-01.

⁸Last accessed 2025-03-19.

⁹Samples can be found on this playlist: <https://suno.com/playlist/24cd7996-6dc5-4125-a391-c9ae54e049a7>.

4 Ethnographic Challenges and Reflection

We now discuss key challenges we encountered during our ethnographic engagement. Drawing on these challenges, we critically reflect on our methodologies and propose potential directions for future research on AI music platforms and their users.

4.1 Challenges

4.1.1 Accessing and Gatekeeping

Accessing specific scenarios, individuals, and communities is a fundamental challenge in any research. In digital ethnography, gaining access to platforms and users for the purpose of entering communities and collecting empirical data can be restricted by the requirement of subscriptions and user accounts. Gatekeeping practices—either performed by company employees, community moderators, or members—may further inhibit researchers from observing, participating, and recruiting informants in communities.

We have accessed the Boomy Discord server as researchers using our real identities, and as pseudonymous users of the platforms. When entering the Discord server as researchers, we have experienced various forms of gatekeeping. This is exemplified by the survey mentioned above, where the A&R team asked us to remove it. After that experience, we realized our presence as researchers on the server was not openly welcomed by the company. We thus contacted users as ourselves through private messaging. Using pseudonymous identities made it easier to participate as a community member without raising suspicion from the company employees or impacting the behavior of other users. Methodologically, this approach can be categorized as covert research, yet where ethical consideration is taken towards participants (Spicker, 2011; Cera, 2023). For example, we minimized online interaction with other users and kept discussions positive about Boomy.

Accessing fans and communities has been challenging in the study of metal music (Varas-Díaz et al., 2016b). As groups that are socially labeled and targeted due to “moral panics” (Cohen, 1972; Hjelm et al., 2011), metal communities tend to guard their subcultural boundaries (Varas-Díaz et al., 2016a). Gaining access involves a process through which members recognize one another and distinguish themselves from outsiders. To those on the outside, metal communities may appear under “closure”, and access often requires navigating a complex set of symbolic practices (Varas-Díaz et al., 2016a, p.102). Digital ethnography introduces additional complexity. On the one hand, AI metal communities maintain certain conventions and symbols of traditional metal culture, such as the boundaries of the community and a critical stance toward the mainstream and authority. On the other hand, their detachment from offline practices and reliance on fully online interactions reshape the communal experience, creating alternative boundaries and forms of connectedness.

Upon accessing the AI metal music communities, the moderator and key community members quickly posted welcome emojis in the public chat to us. However, since we intended to observe and not interact, we chose not to respond. It became apparent later that the moderator interpreted this as a rude form of neglect. When sending private messages that included our real names, affiliations, and research objectives to a few community members in order to recruit informants, the moderator questioned why we were spamming members and noted that we had never posted a greeting on the server. At the same time, based on the feedback from members who responded to us, our researcher identity was questioned regarding its authenticity, and we were suspected of attempting to sell something. One member even sent an email to the research ethics contact listed on the information sheet we provide to informants to confirm we are who we say we are. After the moderator expressed their anger, the majority of members who had initially shown interest in our research stopped responding to our subsequent interaction. We realized that we had not successfully accessed the community and had been subjected to gatekeeping. We chose to respond to the moderator by expressing our sincere apologies and restating our identity and research purpose. At the same time, we stopped sending private messages to any members and continued interviews only with those who had already agreed to participate and signed the consent form.

4.1.2 Building Trust

Building trust is essential for expanding the research, recruiting informants, and gathering valid and reliable data. When appearing under our research identities, it has been challenging to build

trust with Boomy, which may be due to the company feeling suspicious towards being studied by academic researchers, and having a default belief that researchers are critical investigators of their platform. In contrast, building trust with our Boomy informants was relatively easy. The informants we interviewed were generally open and eager to share their experiences.

Building trust within the AI metal music communities has been particularly challenging, as mentioned earlier, due to the scepticism and criticism we received from community gatekeepers. Considering that many participants subsequently lost interest in our research and ceased communication, it can be inferred that they shared negative perceptions of our identity and motivations. Moreover, a few community members who responded to our private messages typically began by asking which of their works we were most interested in, or why we were interested in metal music and their communities. We interpreted these questions as a way of assessing our authenticity and level of engagement. At the same time, some highly cautious participants refused to open any documents—such as our attached interview questions and information sheet—or click on external links, including our project and institutional websites. They also expressed concerns about formally signing informed consent forms. As some informants explained, their past experiences of being targeted by commercial scams and scrutinized by Suno moderators led them to approach our research and identities with suspicion. This skepticism spread easily within the relatively closed community, making it particularly difficult to build trust in a smaller and more homogeneous group.

Additionally, asynchronous online communication and time zone differences significantly hindered timely interaction, leading to prolonged delays in responses. These delays disrupted the natural flow of conversation and, in some cases, led participants to lose patience, reinforcing their initial skepticism. When one party raised a question or concern, replies often arrived hours or even a full day later, occasionally prompting disengagement or complete withdrawal from the exchange. This pattern highlights a key challenge in building digital trust. In niche and subcultural AI music communities, trust typically develops gradually through shared context, ongoing interaction, and mutual recognition. However, the early stages of trust building appear particularly vulnerable to temporal disruptions.

4.1.3 Blurred Positionality of Researchers

Positionality should be considered throughout the entire process of digital ethnography, as the rapidly evolving digital landscape continuously reshapes the assumptions and boundaries of research practices (Quinton and Reynolds, 2017). In this ongoing process of negotiation with “the other” (Collins and McNulty, 2020), researchers must navigate the overlap between their personal and academic selves online, and the shifting power dynamics between researchers and participants (Lavorgna and Sugiura, 2022). As mentioned above, simply by accessing online platforms, we become both researchers and users at the same time. Researchers are further bound by the same platform affordances and constraints as users, which inherently blur the researchers’ personal and public academic identities. This situation makes it difficult for us to adopt clearly defined modes of academic engagement and to distinctly assign or switch between the roles of participant and observer in the field, as was more common in earlier ethnographic research (Gold, 1958; Whiteman, 2012, p.111).

The blurred boundary between observation and participation in digital ethnography presents two interrelated challenges. Firstly, we are often limited to the self-disclosed information that participants choose to share publicly on digital platforms. While private messaging and interviews can offer deeper insights, some informants remain highly guarded—even in interviews—sharing minimal personal details or appearing only as avatars, either to protect their identities, to explore technological possibilities, or both. Secondly, just as researchers may find it difficult to fully access participants’ identities, participants may similarly perceive researchers as distant or anonymous figures hidden behind usernames or institutional affiliations. This perceived opacity creates a challenge for researchers, as it places an additional burden on us to establish a transparent and trustworthy engagement. We are tasked with clearly explaining the nature of the research, how it is conducted, and why participants’ involvement is valuable. Furthermore, there is the challenge of ensuring that informants are fully informed and understand what they are consenting to (Eynon et al., 2017, p.24). For example, one of our Boomy informants seemed to think that we were going to promote their creative work, as an agent or label would. The lack of clarity surrounding our identity and intentions seemed to stem from a misunderstanding of the information sheet or a limited understanding of academic research, with the participant possibly assuming we worked in journalism or marketing.

At the same time, ethnography within AI metal communities has highlighted the shifting power dynamics between researchers and participants. In traditional ethnography, such as during interviews, researchers are typically granted greater power and authority by being positioned as seekers of knowledge with methodological expertise, and regarded as privileged knowers (Nunkoosing, 2005). In this context, as one of us experienced during ethnographic research with metal musicians in offline settings, the informants showed respect for our academic background and expertise, and were cooperative during the interviews. This facilitated more direct access to empirical data and enabled us to recruit additional informants. However, in digital spaces, these dynamics are less clear. The legitimacy and privilege usually associated with researchers do not always apply, complicating the recruitment of informants and conducting interviews. In some cases, this blurred positionality can even become an obstacle to research, as participants may invest effort in verifying the researchers' identities, as mentioned earlier.

4.2 Reflections

In light of the challenges we encountered during the research process, we offer the following reflections. When attempting to access communities moderated by companies, it is crucial to clarify from the outset that the research is not intended to uncover trade secrets or harm the company's reputation. In such contexts, building trust through personal networks, conferences, or industry events can be particularly effective (Seaver, 2022). In niche communities, entering as a newcomer without an established reputation, visible profile, or recognizable identity, can easily raise suspicion—especially if one begins by directly sending private messages. In smaller, more homogeneous groups, where shared experiences and emotional ties shape an “imagined community” (Anderson, 2006), membership is not a fixed status but something earned over time through presence and relational engagement. A more effective approach involves first understanding and becoming familiar with the values, norms, and often unspoken rules of the community. At the same time, it is important to gradually build and refine one's profile as a participant. For instance, creating a public AI music library with a few original creations and engaging in practices across the AI music landscape can demonstrate credibility and commitment. This is not about fabricating a persona or pretending to be someone else, but about understanding the empirical context and gaining the experience of being-in-culture (Markham, 2004, p.145). Based on this foundation, researchers can then reach out to community gatekeepers to seek their approval and introductions. This not only facilitates informant recruitment but also helps ensure that the researcher's presence and intentions are clearly understood and more readily accepted. Such a relational strategy helps to minimize misunderstandings and supports a more ethical and productive research environment.

We argue that sustained and multidimensional immersion in the field is crucial for addressing these challenges. While immersion is a longstanding principle in ethnography (e.g. Bluteau 2021; Hine 2015; Forberg and Schilt 2023)—valued for enabling researchers to learn from participants' perspectives and access insights unavailable from a distance—our experience suggests it is not a static condition. It goes beyond simply spending extended time on a platform or within a community. Rather, immersion is a dynamic, multidimensional process that must adapt depending on the object of engagement—whether it is the companies, the communities, or individual users as discussed above. This understanding is closely linked to another central consideration: the adaptation of the researcher's positionality.

In traditional ethnographic settings, researchers often enter the field with implicit legitimacy or more clearly defined forms of academic engagement. In contrast, on digital platforms, researchers participate under the same circumstances as other users, operating under the same conditions of anonymity, blurred identities, and limited contextual cues. It is thus not sufficient for the researcher to remain solely an observer or participant; instead, they must engage in a dialogue between these perspectives. As Scheper-Hughes (2000) notes, researchers are often faced with “divided loyalties”. They are balancing the goals and methodologies of their research with the need to consider the empirical contexts, including the objects of study and the shifting power dynamics at play (Whiteman, 2012, p.112). To navigate the field effectively, researchers must adapt sustained interaction, iterative involvement, and continuous reflexivity (Davies, 2007). Rather than relying solely on participants' experiences and interpretations, the “ethnographic self” becomes a resource in the research (Collins and Gallinat, 2013). This involves drawing on insights gained through fieldwork, recognizing moments of shared experience with participants, and being transparent about the difficulties and uncertainties involved in making sense of those experiences.

5 Conclusion

As AI music platforms and users continue to grow, AI music is becoming a phenomenon with increasing commercial value and cultural significance. We have discussed our ongoing digital ethnographic research on the AI music platforms Boomy and Suno, as well as their dedicated social platforms on Discord, where we explore the interaction and dynamics between AI music practices, users, and communities. We have mapped the AI music landscape and argued that platforms for music making, music sharing, livestreaming, social media, and online forums are all important to consider how AI music practices and communities emerge and develop. It highlights the field for conducting digital ethnography on AI music and opens up pathways for further exploration of the layered and evolving AI music landscape. Moreover, the rapid changes in the AI music landscape present challenges for digital ethnography. This includes issues of access, gatekeeping, trust-building, and the researcher's shifting positionality. Our Boomy case highlights how our role as researchers—and the questions we asked—clashed with the platform's use as intended by the company moderators. The Suno metal case further illustrates how such communities are moderated and involve gatekeeping based on perceived identity and authenticity. Gaining trust in these smaller communities, therefore, requires a nuanced understanding of their cultural values and norms. This demands a flexible and relational research approach. Our experience shows that the field and the methods shape and affect each other constantly, making it difficult to fully separate methods from the digital fields being studied. Researchers must navigate the roles of both observer and participant while also managing the fluid power dynamics that emerge in interactions with different research subjects. In conclusion, this paper advances digital ethnographic methodologies tailored to the study of AI music and fosters continued critical reflection on research approaches within AI music studies.

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